

The Impact of Employing Some Learning Strategies to Develop Reading Comprehension Skills of 7th & 8th Grade Students at King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence in Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 29, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Reading Comprehension Skills, Mental Visualization Strategy</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5331861</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to investigate the effect of using the "Mental Visualization" strategy in improving reading comprehension at the literal and inferential levels among a sample of 7th and 8th-grade students in King II Abdullah Schools for Excellence. An oral reading test was prepared based on mental visualization strategy and preparing a reading comprehension test. The study individuals were randomly distributed equally into two groups: one experimental and the other control. The pretest was applied to the two groups, and the experimental group was exposed to the mental visualization strategy; while the control group was subjected to the traditional method, the post-test was applied to the two groups. The results indicated statistically significant differences between the students' average scores in the two groups in the overall reading comprehension test and its levels, in favor of the experimental group due to the use of the mental visualization strategy. In addition to the absence of statistically significant differences between the mean scores of students in the total reading comprehension test and its levels, according to the gender variable. The results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between the average scores of the students in the post and follow-up tests, in the overall reading comprehension test and its levels; In the sense of continuing to maintain the positive effect of the mental visualization strategy after two weeks of applying the post-test.</i></p>

Introduction

Reading is a complex and manifold process divided into the skills of word recognition and reading comprehension. The first skill requires the student to know the forms of letters and words and to note the similarities and differences between them while reading comprehension skills include a synchronous extraction process for the skill of introducing students to letter and word shapes and note the similarities and differences between them (Al-Sayed, 2009)

Since reading is so essential and valuable, we had to educate young people to learn its arts and master its skills in general. To master reading comprehension skills in a more specific way, the basic goal of preparing a good reader is to enable him to understand the content of the printed material no matter how difficult it is since the origin of reading is to be first to understand. Hence the importance of reading comprehension skills as a fundamental anchor of the model reading platform.

As al-Maliki (2008:11) points out: "Reading comprehension skills are the basis of all reading processes, has become a central goal in the system of objectives of teaching Arabic in general, the explosion of knowledge and scientific revolution, it makes it necessary to develop the student's skills to analyze the interpretation of the reading, criticism it and evaluate it".

In this context, Gad (2006: 18) points out: "Reading without understanding is no longer a reading in its proper sense" while Suleiman explained (2001) the importance of reading comprehension in the educational process, saying: "Reading comprehension is the basic structure through which the student starts to learn and absorb other educational materials, especially in primary school. Once a student has overcome the difficulty in reading comprehension, they can overcome any problem in understanding the content presented to him. " Thus, the development of reading comprehension skills is a lofty goal of the objectives of teaching reading and literary texts and learning it, as the basis for all literacy processes, and a key factor in mastering the arts of language, and dealing with other sources of knowledge (Alfalit and Al-Zayyat, 2009: 259).

Based on the above, many studies have recommended that students should acquire reading comprehension skills through modern learning methods and develop a plan to teach reading to achieve reading comprehension among students of various stages. Unfortunately, despite the importance of reading skills without other Arabic language skills, as it is and writing are the key to all the doors of knowledge and the treasures of science, however, students suffer from severe difficulties in reading comprehension skills in

general, Al-Hasan and Al-Ghamdi (2011) refer to this as saying: "Because of the importance of reading comprehension, his field has witnessed great research activity in Arab educational circles, where many researchers went to study it in terms its concept, and they find it very difficult, as well as poor performance of teachers who are responsible for its education, because of the negative methods of teaching that they are accustomed to.

Reading comprehension refers to the process of constructing meaning from the written text (chair, 2002), (and the reader's ability to link between his previous knowledge of a topic and the text he is reading (Lerner, 2003), and McLaughlin, 2012) considers that reading comprehension consists of four levels include:

1. Literal level: It refers to the use of less complex skills, including the ability to recognize and understand the main ideas mentioned directly from the read text, and this level refers to "reading the lines".
2. The inferential level: This level refers to the reading that needs not only to understand the apparent overt meaning, but also to understand the implicit meaning. Here the reader must think more than the words and symbols themselves to infer meanings aimed at interpreting the text read "reading between the lines".
3. Organizational level: It requires the reader to have a more understanding of the facts mentioned, and the ability to see the relationships between the materials and identify the important ones and the supporting details.
4. Critical level: It refers to a reading that requires the person to make judgments and evaluate the text; At this level, the reader generalizes, infers, compares, analyzes, and applies the ideas gained in reading (reading beyond the lines).

Thus, poor reading comprehension has long troubled teachers, parents, and intellectuals, and the reasons for this concern only to know the importance of reading in general and the importance of reading comprehension skills in particular. Hence, the efforts of researchers, teachers, and specialized centers in the process of teaching and learning, to offer proposed programs to solve this problem, we have seen many of the methods and strategies of education provided by the researchers as solutions proposed to address the problems of reading comprehension and its difficulties, despite these efforts, and those attempts, but problems of reading comprehension still exist. These problems still attract the interests of researchers and occupy their minds, where they are different in determining the causes of those problems, sometimes attributed to the indifference of the teacher, and other times attributed to the weakness of literacy knowledge and the weakness of the use of teaching aids, while some lack the common denominators between the teacher and the learner, curriculum, literacy, and teaching methods used.

The Problems of the Study

Reading is one of the basic skills that the student needs in order to succeed in all academic subjects in the school, and the student's inability to read means his failure in all academic subjects, whatever their nature, because reading is the basis of the learning process, and without it, the possibility of success at the educational, professional and career levels remains very limited. Difficulty reading is one of the language disorders characterized by the inability to acquire the skills of identifying words and the inability to understand their meanings. Through the researchers' review of several special reports that included an assessment of the reality of the services and programs of the Ministry of Education, it was found that there is a weakness in the level of educational and performance competencies of teachers, as well as the inadequacy of teaching methods and educational curricula and the need to adapt and harmonize teaching methods to match the needs of students, so the need was confirmed to teachers' use of evidence-based instructional strategies to improve students' reading skills. Therefore, the current study dealt with the use of the paraphrasing strategy to develop reading comprehension at its levels (literal and Inferential).

The Study Questions

The study attempted to answer the following main question:

What is the effect of the mental visualization strategy in developing the reading comprehension skills of a sample of students?

The following questions arise from it:

1. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level of ($\alpha=0.05$) in the total score averages on the post-test (literal and inferential) reading comprehension test attributed to the mental visualization strategy)?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the mean score on the post reading comprehension test for each of the reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension) between the sexes attributed to the mental visualization strategy)?

3. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the performance averages on the follow-up reading comprehension test for each of the reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension, Inferential comprehension) attributed to the mental visualization strategy?

Definition of Terms

Self-directed learning: Martiz and Manz, (1991). Defined self-directed learning as learning that involves the learner taking primary responsibility for planning, implementing, and evaluating learning and accepting responsibility for one's thoughts and actions as a learner.

Reading skill

Reading can be defined as an interactive process, the reader and the text, and interacts dynamically with the text as they try to elicit the meaning and where various types of knowledge are being used. Thus, reading skills enable the reader to turn writing into meaning and achieve the goals of independence comprehension.

Mental visualization strategy

Focusing on the good conception of meaning and the quality of the mind's readiness for the deduction, for the student to be able to comprehend what he reads, he must have mental images of the words that he draws in his mind, including:

- Spelling pictures: Draw the correct spelling of a word.
- Phonemes of the word: How to pronounce the sounds of words.
- Semantic image: the meaning of the word.
- Sensory image: the physical symbol that the word actually symbolizes.

Previous Studies

The researcher reviewed some of the studies in the field of reading comprehension

The study of Rusmiati (2017) aimed to improve the reading comprehension of eleventh grade students through the implementation of the (K.W.I) strategy, which consisted of (31) students in the 2016/2017 semester. The data were collected using the achievement test and the observation list, and field notes, there were three phases of the classroom research process. In the first stage, students were unable to implement the (K. W. L) strategy, and many of them were unable to achieve the minimum achievement score of 76. In the second stage, the students were aware of how to implement the K.W.L strategy, so the result was better than the first stage. In the third stage, the students' score was better. Thus, the results of the study showed that K.W.L strategy can improve students' reading comprehension.

The study of Indah (2018) aimed to know the effect of teaching using the (K.W.I) strategy on the reading skill of eighth grade students in the academic year 2017/2018, and its sample consisted of (64) students, (32) students in the experimental group, and (32) students in the control group. The test consisted of (30) items of a multiple-choice type. The results showed that the students who studied using the (K.W.I) strategy had better reading skills than the students who studied without using the (K.W.I) strategy.

Nayak and Sylva (2013) study aimed to investigate the effect of using a directed reading strategy in enhancing the reading comprehension of students learning English as a second language. The study sample consisted of (205) children in the age group (9-10) years in the city of Hong Kong, they were distributed into three groups: the guided reading group, the electronic book group, and the control group that did not receive experimental treatment. The three study groups answered on a test to measure reading comprehension skill, the results indicated that the students of the directed reading group recorded an improvement in reading comprehension compared to the other two study groups.

Pirnayand Ifenthaler (2011) study aimed at revealing the effect of guided reading using computer graphics on facilitating learning in reading comprehension skills. The study sample consisted of (60) male and female students from the University of Friborg. To achieve the objectives of the study, a reading comprehension test was prepared and applied to the experimental and control groups.

As for the study of Al-Shammari (2011), it aimed to reveal the effect of using the guided free reading strategy in improving creative thinking skills: fluency, flexibility, originality, and expansion. The sample of the study consisted of (33) students of the third intermediate grade in the city of Hail, and they were: divided into two groups, control and experimental. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences due to the effect of using the guided free reading strategy in improving some creative thinking skills and the skills as a whole, where the differences were in favor of the experimental group.

Makhzoumi and Batania (2012) study aimed to identify the effect of the strategy of the moon in improving reading comprehension and written expression among the students of the basic stage in Jordan. To achieve this goal, a semi-experimental approach was followed. The researchers chose a sample of the intended

method, consisting of (69) students from the seventh-grade students from two schools, two female divisions, the first is a control group from AJ- Naaimah Comprehensive Secondary School for Girls and was 18 students, and the second was experimental from the same school, and their number was (14) student, and two divisions for males, the first is an officer from the Ibn Taymiyyah Primary School for Boys and their number was (17) student and the second was experimental from the same school, and their number was (20) student, so that the two control divisions (males and females) studied according to the usual method, while the two experimental groups (male and female) studied according to the strategy of "getting the moon" The researchers also designed the study tools of (Reading comprehension test, written expression test). Results showed statistically significant differences due to the impact of the "Get the moon" strategy. The differences were in favor of the experimental group that studied the proposed strategy, the results also showed statistically significant differences due to the interaction between teaching and the strategy, and this interaction between the teaching strategy on the reading comprehension test was in favor of females in the experimental group, in favor of males in the control group.

Al-Mutairi study (2012) The study aimed at finding out the impact of a training program using constructive learning in developing reading comprehension skills among people with learning difficulties in the primary stage in Kuwait. The researcher followed the experimental method in the application of his study, where the study was limited to a sample of the fifth-grade students in the primary stage in Farwaniya Governorate, which reached the final number (61) students, they were divided into two groups, one is experimental taught by the structural learning model. Its number was (30) students, and the other was an experimental group, which was taught in the usual manner, with a total of 31 students. Accordingly, the researcher designed the study tools and materials which were represented in (Non- language intelligence test, reading comprehension test, diagnostic Assessment Scale for Learning Disabilities, the study program based on constructivist learning) the results showed that there were statistically significant differences in post-performance for the visual understanding skills test in favor of the experimental group.

Adnan (2012) study aimed to identify the effectiveness of using multimedia in developing skills (literal understanding, Inferential understanding, critical understanding) for sixth-grade students. To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher used the semi-experimental method, based on the design of the two groups (experimental and control). The researcher designed several tools and research materials for this purpose, represented in (List of reading comprehension skills, multimedia-based software, testing reading comprehension skills). After the researcher verified the validity of the study tools and materials and measured its reliability, it began to apply to the study sample, which reached (50) students of sixth-grader students, in the schools of Al Bamha area in Saudi Arabia, where the number of each group (25) students. The study results revealed statistically significant differences in the post-performance of reading comprehension skills between the experimental and control groups and for the benefit of the experimental group.

The Study Methodology

The Population of the Study

The study population consisted of all 7th and 8th grade students at King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence in the city of Amman in the academic year 2019/2020.

The Study Sample

The individuals participating in the study were selected intentionally from four public schools (King Abdullah Schools for Excellence) in the city of Amman. The individuals participating in the study included (120) male and female students from the seventh and eighth grades, they were selected according to several criteria, namely: that they did not receive any prior training on the use of the "mental visualization" strategy to improve their reading comprehension, and that their results in the reading comprehension pretest did not exceed (50%). They were divided equally into two groups: a control group consisting of (60) male and female students who were taught using the traditional method, of whom (30) males, and (30) females, and an experimental group consisting of (60) male and female students who were taught using the Mental visualization strategy, of whom (30) males, and (30) females. A test to determine the level of pre reading comprehension skills was applied to the two groups to ensure that the members of the two study groups were equal in those skills. Students were selected based on gender (males, females), and grade (seventh and eighth).

Table 1 shows the distribution of study members by group and gender

Table 1: Distribution of study members by group and gender

Group	Gender		N.
	Males	Females	
Experimental	30	30	60
Control	30	30	60

Total	60	60	120
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The Study Tool

Reading Comprehension Test

The test aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses, and to determine the level of reading comprehension in the reading comprehension skills (literal and inferential) of seventh and eighth grade students in King Abdullah II Schools for Excellence. The test contains a number of paragraphs that include the two levels mentioned, and the reading comprehension pretest was applied in order to determine the level of comprehension of the study members, provided that the students' scores in this test do not exceed (50%).

a. 7th grade reading comprehension test

The reading comprehension test for the seventh grade consists of three reading texts within the seventh-grade curriculum of the Arabic language that the students have not previously studied, and includes twenty-six questions; Ten multiple-choice questions, and sixteen structural questions, measure the student's level of literal and inferential reading comprehension. The skills in the test were distributed at the two levels of reading comprehension, where items (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 24, 25, 26) represented the literal level, and items 6, 7, 8 (9, 10, 14, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23) The inferential level, and the scores were distributed on the test items to determine the student's level of the test as follows: (0 = wrong answer), (1 = correct answer), The overall score was (26).

b. 8th grade reading comprehension test

The reading comprehension test for the eighth grade consists of four reading texts within the eighth-grade curriculum for Arabic language that the students have not studied before, under which are thirty questions; Among them are eight multiple-choice questions, and twenty-two structural questions. It measures the student's level in literal and inferential reading comprehension, and the skills in the test were distributed on the two levels of reading comprehension. Paragraphs (1, 2, 5, 8, 9, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25) represented the level literal, and paragraphs 3, 4, 6, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 19, 21, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30) represented the Inferential level. The grades were distributed among the test items to determine the student's level on the test as follows: (0 = wrong answer), (1 = correct answer), and the total score was from (30).

The validity of the test

To verify the apparent validity of the test, it was presented to a group of professors in Jordanian universities, including Arabic language professors, educational supervisors, and Arabic language teachers in schools, which numbered (16) arbitrators, where they were asked to express their opinion on the suitability of the paragraphs to the dimensions and characteristics of the sample, the comprehensiveness of these paragraphs to the content and their suitability for the students of the seventh and eighth grades, and the achievement of the objective for which the test was set, and to express their opinions about the paragraphs in terms of their linguistic formulation and the integrity of the written language, and add any comments they deem appropriate. Their comments and suggestions were taken to simplify some of the paragraphs, and to change their linguistic formulation to suit the level of students.

The Reliability of the Test

To calculate the test's internal reliability coefficient, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used. Referring to the data of a survey sample that consisted of (20) male and female students from the seventh grade, and (20) male and female students from the eighth grade who were chosen from outside the original sample of the study. The test was applied to it twice with an interval of two weeks in the same conditions, and the value of the internal consistency stability coefficient of the seventh-grade total test was (0.70), while the value of the repetition stability coefficient for the seventh grade was (0.661). The value of the internal consistency stability coefficient for the overall test for the eighth grade was also calculated, as it reached (0.72), while the value of the repetition stability coefficient for the eighth grade was (0.825), and Table (2) shows this.

Table 2: Values of Cronbach's alpha coefficient and repeatability coefficient of the test

Grade	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Test/retest reliability coefficient
7th grade	0.70	0.661
8th grade	0.72	0.825

Study Approach

The experimental method was used because of its ability to control the variables, and to note what the independent variable causes in the performance of the experimental group, and it is one of the appropriate approaches to the subject of the study.

O1 X O2 O3 G1
 O1 G2 - O2
 1 = experimental group
 2 = control group
 O1 = Reading Comprehension Pretest
 O2 = Reading Comprehension Posttest
 O3 = Follow-up test
 X = processing "Mental visualization strategy"
 - = the traditional way

The Study Variables

The Independent Variables

1. Gender, and it has two categories (male and female).
2. Teaching method, which has two levels (the method of teaching using (mental visualization) strategy and the traditional method).

The Dependent Variable

Reading comprehension at its literal and inferential levels.

The Study Results

First: the results related to the answer to the first question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level of ($\alpha=0.05$) in the total score averages on the post-test (literal and inferential) reading comprehension test attributed to the mental visualization strategy)?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension and inferential comprehension) were calculated for the post-test depending on the group variable (experimental and control), and a Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was performed as follows:

Table 3: Means and standard deviations of the post-test reading comprehension skills for reading comprehension skills according to the group variable

Group	Statistician	Literalcomprehension	Inferentialcomprehension	Reading comprehension (as a whole)
Experimental	Mean	6.18	4.72	10.57
	Standard deviation	2.13	2.14	2.50
Control	Mean	10.22	9.20	19.37
	Standard deviation	1.96	1.79	2.88

It is evident from Table (3) that the students' performance levels improved in the post-test reading comprehension and in each of his skills in the study groups: experimental and control, however, the performance levels of students in the experimental group were better than the performance levels of students in the control group, as it was found that there were apparent differences in the arithmetic averages of students' performance on the post-total reading comprehension test. The arithmetic mean of the experimental group was (37.19), and for the control group (57.10). In order to show the statistical significance of the differences between the arithmetic averages, the accompanying multiple variance analysis and calculating the effect size was conducted to test the total dimensional reading comprehension and for each of his skills between the two groups (experimental and control), and the results were as in Table (4)

Table 4: Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) for the reading comprehension test and for each of his skills between the two groups in the post-test

Source of variance	Dependentvariable	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	Calculated P	Sig	Impact size
Group	Literalcomprehension	14613.643	1	14613.643	2011.23	*0.000	0.25
	Inferential comprehension	4275.768	1	4275.768	1018.76	*0.000	0.30

	Total	3207.788	1	3207.788	825.47	*0.000	0.29
ERROR	Literalcomprehension	421.442	58	7.266			
	Inferential comprehension	243.421	58	4.197			
Total	Total	225.415	58	3.886			
	Literalcomprehension	15035.084	59				
	Inferential comprehension	4519.189	59				
	Total	3433.203	59				

* Significant at level (0.05)

Table (4) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the significance level (05.0) between the average scores of the students in the two groups, in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of his skills. These differences came in favor of the experimental group, by referring to Table (3) for comparison between the mean values of the two groups.

Second: The results related to the answer to the second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the mean score on the post reading comprehension test for each of the reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension) between the sexes attributed to the mental visualization strategy?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension and inferential comprehension) were calculated for the post-test of the experimental group according to the gender variable, as in Table (5) and Table (6).

Table 5: T-test for independent samples to test reading comprehension and for each of its skills according to the gender variable for seventh grade students

Skill	Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	P value	Sig
Literalcomprehension	Male	14	9.00	1.92	0.881	0.386
	Female	16	8.06	3.55		
Inferential comprehension	Male	14	6.64	3.34	-1.22	0.231
	Female	16	8.00	2.73		
Reading comprehension (as a whole)	Male	14	15.29	4.63	-0.433	0.669
	Female	16	16.13	5.82		

Table (5) shows that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the mean scores of seventh grade students in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of his skills according to the gender variable.

Table 6: T-test for independent samples to test reading comprehension and for each of its skills according to the gender variable for eighth grade students

Skill	Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	P value	Sig
Literalcomprehension	Male	14	7.43	2.42	-0.94	0.353
	Female	16	8.42	3.33		
Inferential comprehension	Male	14	5.99	2.84	-1.13	0.265
	Female	16	7.20	2.95		
Reading comprehension (as a whole)	Male	14	13.33	4.38	-1.01	0.317
	Female	16	15.23	5.83		

Table (6) shows that there are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of eighth grade students in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of his skills according to the gender variable.

Based on the individual assessment of each male and female student after teaching using mental visualization, it was found that there were no differences in performance due to gender.

Third: Results related to the answer to the third question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the performance averages on the follow-up reading comprehension test for each of the reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension, Inferential comprehension) attributed to the mental visualization strategy?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of reading comprehension skills (literal comprehension and inferential comprehension) were calculated for the post-test and the follow-up test, and the results of the t-test for the correlated samples as in Table (7) and Table (8).

Table 7: T-test of the related samples to test reading comprehension and for each of his skills in the post and follow-up tests for seventh grade students

Skill	Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	P value	Sig
Literalcomprehension	Posttest	30	10.47	1.92	0.190	0.850
	Follow-up test	30	10.33	1.91		
Inferential comprehension	Posttest	30	9.73	1.44	0.121	0.905
	Follow-up test	30	9.67	1.59		
Reading comprehension (as a whole)	Posttest	30	20.20	2.54	0.287	0.776
	Follow-up test	30	19.93	2.55		

Table (7) shows that there are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of seventh grade students in the tests, in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of his skills, meaning there is a positive effect of the training program on reading comprehension.

Table 8: T-test of the related samples to test reading comprehension and for each of his skills in the post and follow-up measurements for eighth grade students

Skill	Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	P value	Sig
Literalcomprehension	Posttest	30	9.97	2.03	200	0.91
	Follow-up test	30	9.97	1.97		
Inferential comprehension	Posttest	30	8.67	1.98	0.305	0.763
	Follow-up test	30	8.45	1.91		
Reading comprehension (as a whole)	Posttest	30	18.55	3.03	0.214	0.832
	Follow-up test	30	18.32	2.89		

Table (8) shows that there are no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of eighth grade students in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of its skills, meaning that there is a positive effect of using the mental visualization strategy on reading comprehension, and the positive impact of the mental visualization strategy on comprehension continues to be maintained on reading as a whole two weeks after applying the post-test.

Discussion of the Results

The results showed a significant improvement in reading comprehension at its two levels: (literal and inferential) among the students in the experimental group who studied. Using a mental visualization strategy. The researchers attribute the reason for this improvement to the effect of using the mental visualization strategy, which led to a clear improvement in the grades of the students who were subjected to it. The researchers believe that this is due to reasons related to the implementation procedures, which were represented in the accuracy and clarity of the procedures for implementing the strategy, its application under appropriate conditions, the implementation of the strategy individually for students in small groups, the cooperation of teachers in creating an appropriate atmosphere for the application, and the cooperation of participating students in terms of commitment to attendance and adherence to instructions Calm and positive interaction with the teacher. This is also due to the clarity and integrity of the language used during the implementation of the strategy.

The results also indicated that the students' scores on the post-test reading comprehension test in the experimental group for the level of literal reading comprehension were slightly higher than their scores on the level of inferential reading comprehension. This is due to the capabilities of the students; As the literal level requires the student to have fewer complex skills than the reading comprehension skills represented in direct understanding of the reading text. As for the deductive level, it needs not only to understand the apparent overt meaning, but also to understand the implicit meaning of the text (Lerner,2003).

The results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the students in the post and follow-up tests, in the overall reading comprehension test and in each of his skills.

This indicates that the positive effect of using the mental visualization strategy on students' scores continues to be maintained two weeks after applying the post-test, without a decline in students' performance. The researchers attribute this to the effectiveness of the mental visualization strategy in making the reading material more understandable through the sequence of the steps of the strategy and its clarity and by motivating the student to link previous knowledge to reach what is already known to him about the subject, and thus facilitates linking current learning to previous learning (Kletzien, 2009).

Recommendations

After discussing the results, the study came up with the following recommendations:

1. Conducting studies on the effectiveness of the mental visualization strategy in improving reading comprehension at the critical and creative levels and with different variables in the educational stages (basic, intermediate, and secondary).
2. Training teachers at all levels to use the mental visualization strategy in educational situations.

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